

«YOUTH BOOK» - THE DOOR OF WIDE OPPORTUNITIES.

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Annotation: The article discusses the implementation of state youth policy at a new stage of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the issues of the «Youth Book», created to support young people.

Keywords: “Youth book”, “Youth balance”, “youth book.uz” measures, youth, state policy, employment.

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been doing a lot to educate young people in the spirit of respect for national and universal values, to raise a spiritually mature and physically healthy generation, to protect their rights and interests. In particular, the state has created a system of socio-economic, organizational and legal measures to create conditions for the social formation of young people and the development of their intellectual, creative and other potential. possible.

In order to raise the system of work with young people in Uzbekistan to a new level, to establish permanent financial sources and the order of their use in order to effectively organize the work of their social, legal and psychological support, vocational training and employment On March 11, 2021, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted Resolution No. 132. It was this decision that approved the model charter of the Youth Support Fund, which is included in the «Youth Book». Funds from the Youth Book Fund include:

- BHM for financially disadvantaged young people included in the «Youth Book»

To provide one-time financial assistance in the amount of up to 4 times;

- to cover up to 75% of the expenses of non-governmental educational organizations on entrepreneurship and vocational training of young people;

- For young people included in the «Youth Book» to cover the cost of renting non-residential premises for a period of up to 12 months for a period of entrepreneurial activity and self-employment, up to 25 times the BHM per year;

- Allocate a subsidy of up to 40 times the BHM for young people included in the «Youth Book» to start a business and purchase the necessary equipment and tools for self-employment;

- Children from families enrolled in the «Iron Book» studying at universities in the country to pay up to 50% of the contract amount, but not more than 50 times the BHM;

- The children included in the «Iron Book» will be reimbursed for the cost of treatment of seriously ill children in the country or abroad in the amount not exceeding 50 times the BHM.

Speaking about the «Youth Book» as part of the implementation of state youth policy in Uzbekistan, it should be noted that in recent years in our country the population, including women and youth in need of social protection, living conditions are difficult, unemployed and unprofessional. - A completely new system of targeted state assistance has been introduced to citizens who do not have a profession and need legal and moral and psychological support. In order to organize targeted and individual work with each person in this direction, a completely new «Iron Book» for families in need of financial assistance and support - social, economic, legal, psychological support - Implemented the «Women's Book» and «Youth Book» systems for women and youth with the need and desire for support, knowledge and vocational training, respectively.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev to further improve the support system, to promote their employment, to encourage entrepreneurial ideas and initiatives, to create additional conditions for them to earn a decent income, to take the work in this area to a new level. Decree PF-6208 of April 20, 2006 was approved. The order was introduced in accordance with the decree on the involvement of young people in entrepreneurship, their permanent employment, the creation of favorable conditions for additional income.

In the country's public policy, the issue of the youth, who make up 64.0% of the population, has been on the agenda. That is why today these processes have a special place in the policy of the President, which is based on justice and humanity, directly pursued by the President.

As the head of state said, “It is time to take our work to a new level, to create modern jobs for our children and ensure that they take their rightful place in life. All the forces and opportunities of our state and society will be mobilized for the development and happiness of our young people, who are independent-minded, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, and are equal to their peers in any field in the world.”

In the implementation of the state youth policy in the new Uzbekistan, systematic work is being carried out in our country aimed at the harmonious

upbringing of the younger generation, the creation of all necessary conditions for them to take an independent step in life.

In his speech at the joint session of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis dedicated to the inauguration of the newly elected President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, he said: the planned priorities were discussed.

In it, the head of our state said, "We will continue to focus on educating our young people, especially girls, to be healthy and mature, to realize their abilities and talents, to develop in the spirit of love and devotion to the Motherland, national and universal values. «It's a big deal,» he said. This means that in the next five years of development of our country, youth issues will again become a priority.

In conclusion, studying the work done on youth policy in our country, we can see that measures are being taken in our country to form a harmoniously developed generation, to educate young people spiritually, morally and physically healthy, to make them active participants in ongoing reforms. we can see.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Together we will build a free and prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan. T.: Uzbekistan. 2016.
2. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 132 of March 11, 2021.
3. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 250 of 28.04.2021.
4. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. T.: Uzbekistan. 2017
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 20.04.2021 Decree No. PF-6208.
6. Speech of the newly elected President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the joint session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dedicated to the inauguration ceremony. 06.11.21.

